

ADVANCED MICRO-MECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF HIGHLY LOADED HYBRID COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

A.E. Scott, M. Clinch*, W. Hepples*, N. Kalantzis, I. Sinclair, S.M. Spearing
Engineering Materials and Surface Engineering, School of Engineering Sciences
University of Southampton, Southampton, SO17 1BJ
* Luxfer Gas Cylinders, Colwick, Nottingham,
anna.scott@soton.ac.uk, Mike.Clinch@luxfer.net, Warren.Hepples@luxfer.net,
nk503@soton.ac.uk, I.Sinclair@soton.ac.uk, S.M.Spearing@soton.ac.uk

SUMMARY

Multi-scale computed tomography has been used to obtain a detailed 3D understanding of meso- and micro-structural characteristics in a hybrid composite/metallic component, along with a micro-mechanical understanding of the associated failure processes. A 3D FE approach has been adopted to model the structure, which has been informed by results achieved from the computed tomography.

Keywords: Filament Wound, Hybrid Structure, Computed Tomography, Finite Element Analysis

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are well known to display a range of complex failure modes, depending on material and load environment. Physically-sound structural performance optimisation must be based on micro-mechanical analyses that accurately reflect the material's structure and behaviour. The present work explores the integration of advanced 3D imaging methods with finite element modelling, particularly in terms of model initialisation and identification of failure modes.

High-resolution x-ray computed tomography, CT, is gaining interest as an ideal tool for material mechanics studies [1]. It is an established non-invasive method to create 3D images in the micrometer and sub-micrometer range of solid objects, commonly known in medical terms of 'CAT' scanning ('computed axial tomography'). The method is gaining importance in engineering and materials science to determine the internal characteristics of materials and structures [2]. In the case of polymer composite studies, it can be used to identify characteristics such as fibre orientation and volume fraction at the sub-ply level, and failure mechanisms such as ply cracks and individual fibre breaks [1]. The detailed damage characterisation available via CT (*i.e.* potentially complete internal 3D mapping of cracks as they form) enables significant innovative opportunities in terms of both model initialisation and validation.

As with most imaging, the resolution of a CT scan usually scales with the size of the region viewed. Given the multi-scale nature of hybrid composite structure behaviour (from overall geometry effects, to individual ply behaviour, to fibre-matrix interactions)

a multi-scale imaging approach is appropriate, as illustrated in Figure 1. In particular micro-focus CT (μ CT) technology has been used to provide images at moderate to low resolutions, Fig. 1 (a) and (b), from whole component samples and sectioned sub-regions. Synchrotron radiation computed tomography (SRCT) scans of critical regions of interest may then be obtained with resolutions of less than $1\mu\text{m}$, Fig. 1 (c), providing structural information down to single fibre levels.

Figure 1: Multi-scale CT imaging approach of a hybrid composite-metallic structure: (a) & (b): μ CT scans of whole structure and sub-region. (c): SRCT image of plies and local fibre distribution

MATERIALS & METHODS

Materials

Analysis was carried out on loaded and unloaded experimental carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy filament wound aluminium hoop structures. The overall diameter was 90mm, with aluminium, carbon and glass layer thicknesses corresponding to ~ 2 , 2 and 0.5mm respectively. A uniform internal load was applied to the structures until fracture occurred. Acoustic emission sensors were used to monitor the sub-critical damage processes during loading, indicating key regions of interest for subsequent imaging, *i.e.* identification of sub-critical damage evolution.

Computed Tomography

μ CT images were taken using an X Tek™ Benchtop 160Xi scanner. A focal spot size down to $\sim 3\mu\text{m}$ is achievable for objects in the 3-5mm size range. Higher resolution SRCT images were achieved at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) in Grenoble, with small regions of interest (selected via acoustic emission and μ CT scanning) being imaged with a resolution of $1.4\mu\text{m}$ in this work. Beamline ID19 was particularly used in the near-field Fresnel regime, providing both adsorption and phase contrast.

CT imaging was carried out on both the loaded and unloaded structures as follows:

- Macro-structure: imaging of the whole sample diameter using the μ CT at a resolution of $\sim 75\mu\text{m}$.
- Meso-structure: small regions of interest imaged at a resolution of $\sim 8\mu\text{m}$. These were extracted from the complete hoop by first cutting short cylindrical sections, mounting them in epoxy (to constrain and prevent the release of residual stresses and corresponding delamination of the structure), then cutting approximately rectangular sections of $\sim 20\text{mm}$ width.
- Micro-structure: sub-regions were extracted from the meso-structure samples above, using a slow speed diamond saw, to image at ESRF in narrow ‘matchsticks’, $\sim 2\text{mm}$ in cross-section and $\sim 20\text{mm}$ length.

The software packages VGStudio Max™ 1.2.1, ImageJ™ and Aphelion™ 3.2 were used to analyse the reconstructed CT images to determine the internal material characteristics and segment and highlight particular features of interest.

Modelling

The Finite Element Analysis package ANSYS™ 11 was used to simulate the behaviour of the hybrid structure subjected to internal load. In the first instance, an elastic model was used to determine stress distributions to give a 3D model of the overall component. A 30-degree section of the hoop structure was modelled, with classical laminate plate theory (CLPT) and basic structural mechanics being used to validate the hoop and axial stresses found in the 3D model. An elastic/plastic model was then created, using the multi-scale imaging to inform the model of macro and micro-mechanical features to provide a more realistic simulation. This was carried out by updating the corresponding fibre volume fraction and local composite geometry determined in the CT images.

The Al-alloy, carbon and glass composite layers of the component were represented by 3D 20-node structural solid elements with the composite layers presenting both circumferential and near-longitudinal wound plies. The effective properties of the composite materials at the corresponding angles were calculated using CLPT. In the elastic/plastic model the Al-alloy was modelled as a non-linear material described by a simple Von Mises yield criterion and a bilinear kinematic hardening law.

RESULTS

Computed Tomography Material Characterisation

It has been possible to determine various material characteristics from the various multi-scale images. On a macro-scopic level the ply geometry can easily be determined, with Figure 2 showing variations in the thickness of the various layers near the conical end region of the component.

The meso-scale images reveal the tow ply angles and local ply thickness variations. The ply angles can be seen in Figure 3, where some of the CFRP layer has been cut away via

image processing to reveal the plies. Figure 4 shows a variation in the thickness of the CFRP layer, revealing an apparent correlation in local void content with layer thickness.

The micro-scale images enable the individual fibre angles to be identified, Figure 5. Figure 6 shows individual fibres in the CFRP layer, which can be used to determine the local volume fraction down the single fibre level (*e.g.* via tessellation).

Figure 2 : μ CT slice image of conical end region showing variations in layer thicknesses.

Figure 3: 3D μ CT image of local region of Al-alloy and carbon composite: CFRP has been cut away (within the volume image) to show ply angles, emphasised by the black arrows.

Figure 4: 2D μ CT slice of sample wall: arrow highlights a variation in the thickness of the CFRP layer

Figure 5: 2D SRCT slice of CFRP layer showing local ply angle and defects

Figure 6: 2D SRCT slice of individual fibres

Computed Tomography Failure Mechanisms

The images from the loaded and unloaded components provide an insight into the failure mechanisms that occur prior to overall fracture. The meso-scale images enable cracks in the CFRP layers to be identified. Figure 7 shows a crack running from the

interface between two CFRP wound layers (the images also show ring artefacts, centred on the rotation axis of the scan in the middle of CFRP layer 1, not to be confused with the component structure). In Figure 8 it can be seen that cracking runs parallel with the circumference within layers, with periodic steps within the ply thickness.

High resolution SRCT images allow matrix damage to be identified at a much higher resolution, as shown in Figure 9, along with the incidence of individual fibre breaks, as seen in Figure 10. The frequency of fibre fracture was quantified, occurring in the circumferentially wound layers of the CFRP, with a frequency approximately 4 times more in the inner-most ply (*i.e.* the ply next to the aluminium layer) compared to the outer layer.

Figure 7: x,z plane image of a crack (highlighted in blue and voids in red): (a) showing general crack location, (b) detail in relation to the circumferential (layer 1 & 3) and longitudinal (layer 2) CFRP.

Figure 8: 3D image of crack from Figure 7, highlighted in red. Aluminium and glass composite layers are rendered partially opaque to illustrate the component geometry.

Figure 9: 2D high resolution image of intralaminar matrix cracks in CFRP after loading.

Figure 10: CT image showing single fibre breaks resulting from loading.

Modelling Results

Figure 11 shows a 3D map of the hoop stress found in the elastic/plastic model of the component. As noted above, the model was updated to include composite geometry and fibre volume fraction determined from the CT images. On-going model development is designed to address local structure and micro-mechanical issues such as defect distribution and fibre heterogeneity via a local/global approach. Whilst a full micro-mechanical analysis will require such a method, initial modelling results are seen to be consistent with micro-mechanical findings, with the frequency of fibre failure correlating with the predicted stress partitioning between the composite plies.

Figure 11: 3D FE model of section of hoop structure, showing hoop stress (in Pa).

CONCLUSION

The imaging techniques used in this paper provide highly detailed quantification of both the underlying structure and failure events that occur prior to failure. Where existing macro- and micro-scale models of such structures base their work on estimated micro-mechanical behaviour, mathematical models and empirical parameters [3],[4] and [5], the present work can provide direct physical verification of the events to inform model formulation. Multi-scale imaging is seen to be particularly relevant to hierarchical nature of composite and hybrid structures, enabling a thorough analysis of the present hybrid structure. The material characteristics found in the CT images have been successfully used to inform a 3D finite element model to give an initial understanding of the stress distribution within the component that is consistent with the observed onset of the failure.

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